

FACTORS INFLUENCING ONLINE HEALTH INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOUR AMONG MANAGEMENT UNDERGRADUATES IN A SELECTED NATIONAL UNIVERSITY, SRI LANKA

Pavithra Wijesingha¹, Amitha Padukkage²

¹*University of Sri Jayewardenepura, pavimw96@gmail.com*

²*University of Sri Jayewardenepura, amitha@sjp.ac.lk*

Introduction

Background of the Research Study

The Internet is an effective medium for the communication of information on various aspects. As of 2019, estimated Internet users were 3.97 billion worldwide (Johnson, 2021). An increased number of people are searching the internet for different types of knowledge, such as health-related information, educational materials, access to online databases, exploring the application of theoretical concepts and using various interactive methods to improve comprehension of complex ideas (Shamimi & Aini, 2018). Young people are the most active users among all the age groups, who use internet channels to search knowledge and connect with others (Obasola & Agunbiade, 2016). According to Digital and Social Media Marketing Stats and Facts of Sri Lanka (2018), 6.71 million individuals use the internet, where the proportion is 32 percent of the total population. With modern trends, internet users can access different types of information which they need in their daily life, their studies, and other requirements.

Users need set of skills to use online health information and utilize that information for their health decision making. Therefore the ability to seek, find, understand, and evaluate online health information and apply the knowledge gained to health decision making is referred as eHealth literacy (Norman & Skinner, 2006). Health information-seeking behaviour is a demonstration of self-health management (Ahadzadeh & Sharif, 2017). Therefore, that behaviour would encourage personal health knowledge,

compose their judgments, beliefs, and attitudes toward a healthy lifestyle in terms of behaviour and also motivate them to finally make an educated decision on health (Ahadzadeh & Sharif, 2017). On the other hand, Health information-seeking behaviour (HISB), or Internet health information is a guide to increase the quality of life and improving the health status of a person. Therefore, the information taken from online resources has become a substantial part of daily life (Waigandt, 2017).

Research Problem

There are a number of studies to identify the factors influencing online health information-seeking behaviour of different groups such as clinical students, nursing students and health care providers in world context (Ghaddar et al., 2012; Laki., 2016; Shamimi & Aini., 2018). However, literature on online health information seeking behaviour in Sri Lankan context is very lacking.

With the advancement of Internet technologies, a large percentage of the students are adopting Internet technologies for their daily life. E-mails and instant messaging are the most common communication platforms and social media, and web are the common information search platforms (Escoffery et al., 2005; Jones, 2002). Usage of internet facilities among undergraduates in Sri Lanka has greatly increased especially through availability of free Wi-Fi facilities and use of smart phones. Although there is a high usage of Internet, use online sources to solve undergraduates' health issues by using online health information is very lacking. This study therefore seeks to identify factors influencing online health information seeking behaviour among management undergraduates in Sri Lanka.

Research Objectives

1. To identify the factors influencing online health information-seeking behaviour of management undergraduates.

2. To identify the relationship between the factors and the online health information-seeking behaviour of management undergraduates.

Conceptual Framework of the study

Many researchers have created different models to identify factors influencing online health information seeking behaviour. Conceptual framework of this study, which is illustrated in figure 1, was developed based on the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) developed by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen as an improvement over Information Integration Theory (Ajzen, 2014). There are 5 constructs in this model. Attitudes towards intention to seek online health information and subjective norms are directly affecting the behaviour intention to seek online health information. Behaviour intention and eHealth literacy are the variables that directly affect online health information seeking behaviour.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The following hypotheses were developed to assess the relationship between factors and the Online health information seeking behaviour.

H1: There is a positive relationship between Behaviour Intention on online health information seeking behaviour and online health information seeking behaviour.

H2: There is a positive relationship between e-Health literacy and online health information seeking behaviour.

H3: There is a positive relationship between Attitudes towards intention to seek online health information and behaviour intention on online health information seeking behaviour

H4: There is a positive relationship between Subjective Norms on intention to seek online health information and behaviour intention on online health information seeking behaviour.

Design of the study

This study was conducted as a quantitative cross-sectional study. The population interested in this study was all the management undergraduates in the National Universities of Sri Lanka. As a limitation of this study, all the management undergraduates could not be covered within the given time frame. As a result, this study collected responses from management undergraduates at the selected one National University. According to the ex-ante power analysis tool, the minimum required sample size for 0.05 probability level was 91. The sample population was selected using a convenience sampling technique. Collection of data was carried out under the primary data collection method using an online questionnaire instrument. Data were analysed through descriptive analysis, validity and reliability testing and finally, hypotheses testing using SmartPLS 3 software.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive analysis

Around 64% (58/91) of respondents were female and 36% (33/91) were male respondents. Most of the respondents rated their own health status as good (53%, 48/91) or very good (36%, 33/91) or excellent (7%, 6/91) while 4% (4/91) rated their own health status as poor. All the respondents have used the internet and half of respondents use the internet several times a day (50%, 45/91). Majority of the undergraduates (90%, 82/91) use smartphones as a connecting device to the Internet. As the source of health information, most respondents use social media (eg: Facebook, Twitter) (78%, 71/91), video sharing sites (eg: YouTube) (71%, 65/91) or Online encyclopaedia (eg: Wikipedia) (33%, 30/91). Lack of time (76%, 69/91) is the highly concerning barrier that hampers the access to above mentioned health sources on the internet. Lack of reading culture (55%, 50/91), Unreliability of the resources (37%, 34/91) and Lack of skills to search health information (22%, 20/91) are the other most relevant barriers that can be identified.

Reliability and Validity Analysis

Indicator Reliability

As shown in table 1, all the items' loadings are greater than 0.7 as suggested by Hair et al. (2011) and thus the indicator reliability was demonstrated.

Internal Consistency

All Cronbach's Alpha & Composite reliability values which are shown in table 1 are greater than 0.7 as suggested by Hair et al. (2011) and thus internal consistency was established.

Convergent Validity Analysis

As suggested by Hair et al. (2011), all the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values are greater than 0.5 and thus Convergent validity was demonstrated.

Table 1. Summary of Reliability and Validity Analysis

	Item Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Attitude		0.921	0.944	0.808
AT1	0.884			
AT2	0.909			
AT3	0.923			
AT4	0.878			
Behaviour Intention		0.863	0.917	0.785
BI1	0.88			
BI2	0.872			
BI3	0.907			
Health Literacy		0.934	0.945	0.685
HL1	0.859			
HL2	0.757			
HL3	0.862			
HL4	0.872			
HL5	0.87			
HL6	0.834			
HL7	0.718			
HL8	0.834			
Online health information seeking behaviour		0.948	0.959	0.794
OB1	0.874			
OB2	0.878			
OB3	0.904			
OB4	0.869			
OB5	0.903			
OB6	0.918			

Subjective Norms		0.933	0.957	0.882
SN1	0.949			
SN2	0.913			
SN3	0.955			

Discriminant Validity Analysis

As represented in below table 2, none of the constructs' cross-correlations (off-diagonal elements) exceeded the respective square root of each construct's AVE (diagonal elements), thus discriminant validity was demonstrated (Hair et al., 2011).

Table 2. Summary of Discriminant Validity

	Attitudes	Behaviour Intention	Online health information seeking behaviour	Subjective norms	eHealth literacy
Attitudes	0.899				
Behaviour Intention	0.765	0.886			
Online health information seeking behavior	0.604	0.613	0.891		
Subjective Norms	0.687	0.668	0.498	0.939	
eHealth literacy	0.539	0.521	0.723	0.577	0.828

Hypothesis Testing

Behaviour intention and eHealth literacy were both found to have a significant path to online health information seeking behaviour respectively 0.324 ($p < 0.01$) and 0.554 ($p < 0.01$). Similarly, Attitudes towards intention to seek online health information and Subjective Norms were both found to

have a significant path to Behaviour intention towards the online health information seeking and respectively 0.579 ($p < 0.01$) and 0.270 ($p < 0.01$).

Table 3. Summary of the Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses	Path Coefficient	P Value
H1: BI->OHISB	0.324	0.001
H2: eHL->OHISB	0.554	0.000
H3: Att->BI	0.579	0.000
H4: SN->BI	0.270	0.001

Conclusion

The main findings were as follows.

H1: As per the study, it proves that behaviour intention towards seeking health information online has a significant positive impact on online health information seeking behaviour ($P < 0.05$, 0.001). This indicates that behaviour intention is positively influencing online health information seeking behaviour. Literature suggests that there is a significant relationship between the behaviour intention and the actual behaviour (Ajzen, 2014). Therefore, the finding is compatible with those relationships with regard to online health information seeking behaviour.

H2: This study proves that e-Health literacy has a significant positive impact on online health information seeking behaviour ($P < 0.05$, 0.000). This indicates that e-Health literacy is positively influencing for the management undergraduates in their online health information seeking behaviour. This is compatible with the results of previous study done by Wong & Cheung (2019), which indicates positive impact of eHealth literacy on online health information seeking behaviour.

H3: As per the study, it proves that attitude towards seeking health information online has a significant positive impact on behaviour intention to seek online health information ($P < 0.05$, 0.000). This indicates that attitude towards seeking online health information is a predictor of behaviour intention to seek online health information. This finding is also compatible with the findings of Ahmad and Khan (2017) where it indicated that there is a significant positive effect of attitude on intention to seek health information.

H4: This study proves that subjective norms have a significant positive impact on behaviour intention to seek online health information ($P < 0.05$, 0.001). This indicates that subjective norm is another predictor of behaviour intention to seek online health information. This is again consistent with the previous study done by Xia et al. (2017) and this study found that subjective norm has a positive influence on user intention where the stronger subjective norm, the stronger the user intention of online health information seeking.

Theoretical Contribution

Though there were many studies on the topic; online health information seeking behaviour among different context such as clinical students, nursing students, and health care providers in world context as well as Sri Lankan context, there were no proper study in the Sri Lankan context on online health information seeking behaviour, especially among Management Undergraduates. This research provides empirical findings on factors influence on online health information seeking behaviour in Sri Lankan context.

Further, it theoretically contributes to extending the application of the Theory of Reasoned Action model and online health information seeking behaviour in Sri Lankan context.

Practical Contribution

Most of the health care providers in both the government and private sector expect to use new technologies to provide health information for the general public. The findings of this study can be used by clinicians to plan e-Health interventions, as well as by IT developers to design and develop e-Health strategies for younger groups, particularly University students in Sri Lanka. Further this study highlights the sources of online health information mostly used by the younger groups and barriers. Therefore, health care providers can get more understanding about how they can spread their health services through these identified sources.

Limitations and future Research

With the limited time frame and for other reasons, this study has faced some limitations. The following are the limitations and future research domains.

- The study focused on the behaviour of online health information seeking on the management undergraduates in selected National University. In order to have a good understanding of the factors affecting online health information seeking behaviour among Management Undergraduates in Sri Lanka, it is important to focus on all other Universities of the country. There are 15 Universities which are registered under the University Grants Commission in Sri Lanka and it is imperative to understand the status in other Universities as well. Hence, the focus of the study being only on a single University in Sri Lanka limited the study.
- With the limited time, since responses were collected through the online google form researcher could not interact with the respondents directly. Direct responses may lead to the more trustworthy responses as this in health related studies.
- This study was limited to the TRA model and the most cited factor is eHealth literacy. There are many more factors that affect the online health information seeking behaviour and should be studied further.

- More than half of the responses are from the Department of Information Technology. Therefore, they are having more IT literacy than other department undergraduates since they are more engaged with technology. This may lead to the misleading results of the study.

References

Ahadzadeh, A. S. and Sharif, S. P. (2017) 'Online health information seeking among Malaysian women: Technology acceptance model perspective', *SEARCH (Malaysia)*, 9(1), pp. 47–70.

Ahmad, A. and Khan, M. N. (2017) 'Students Seeking Health-related Information over Internet: An Empirical Study', *Journal of Health Management*, 19(2), pp. 352–367.

Ajzen, I. and Gilbert Cote, N. (2008) Attitudes and the prediction of behavior In *Attitudes and persuasion*, New York:Psychology Press, pp. 289–311.

Escoffery, C., Miner, K. R., Adame, D. D., Butler, S., McCormick, L. and Mendell, E. (2005) 'Internet use for health information among college students', *Journal of American College Health*, 53(4), pp. 183–188.

Ghaddar, S. F., Valerio, M. A., Garcia, C. M. and Hansen, L. (2012) 'Adolescent health literacy: The importance of credible sources for online health information' *Journal of School Health*, 82(1), pp. 28–36.

Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M. and Sarstedt, M. (2011) 'PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet', *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 19(2), pp. 139–152.

Johnson, J. (2021) *Internet Usage Worldwide – Statistics & Facts*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/topics/1145/internet-usage-worldwide/> (Accessed: 31 May 2021).

Jones S. (2002) *The Internet Goes to College: How Students Are Living in the Future with Today's Technology*. Available at: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED472669> (Accessed: 7 Sep 2020).

Laki, D. G. (2016) 'Factors Influencing Health Information-seeking Behavior among Health Care Providers at Health Facilities in Tanga Region: A Case Study of Muhef Project', *Universal Journal of Public Health*, 4(6), pp. 279–297.

Norman, C. D. and Skinner, H. A. (2006) 'eHEALS: The eHealth Literacy Scale', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 8, pp1–7.

Obasola, O. I. and Agunbiade, O. M. (2016) 'Online Health Information Seeking Pattern Among Undergraduates in a Nigerian University', *Sage Open*, 6(1).

Shamimi, A.A.N.I. and Aini, M.Z.N. (2018) 'Factors Influencing Behavioral Intention in Online Health Information Seeking among Public University Students', *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(7).

Waigandt, A. W. K. (2017) *Effects of health information seeking behaviors on anxiety, and loss among East Asian international students*, Ph. D., University of Missouri—Columbia

Wong, D. K. K. and Cheung, M. K. (2019), 'Online health information seeking and ehealth literacy among patients attending a primary care clinic in Hong Kong: A cross-sectional survey', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 21(3).

Xia, L., Deng, S. and Liu, Y. (2017) 'Seeking Health Information Online: The Moderating Effects of Problematic Situations on User Intention', *Journal of Data and Information Science*, 2(2), pp. 76–95.